

AN INSIGHT INTO THE SOCIO-PSYCHO CONTEXTS AND MODUS OPERANDI OF SOUTH AFRICA'S WORST SERIAL KILLERS OVER TIME

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Abstract

Over the years, several myths have been peddled within societies and academic circles in relation to exploring the mysterious lives of serial killers. Socio-psycho factors have been used to explain some of their criminal behaviour. Some mythologies about serial killers are that most of them are loners, abused children, and sexually motivated killers. Some researchers have also attributed mental challenges, drugs, and alcohol as possible motives for serial killers. In some instances, some serial killers have confessed to heard unknown controlling voices, urging them to kill their victims. We are not in a rational or neutral position to know whether voices, hearing by serial killers, are actually factual experiences or not. However, to enter a plea of insanity for murder is widely known with the criminal law field. This is the reason why in some cases, offenders are accessed to ascertain their fitness to stand trial. This article deals with a very serious challenging crime and highlights the safety of citizens. The article has three aims, first, to explore and debunk the secretive world of serial killers. Second, to explore the serial killer's motives and modus operandi. Third, to highlight the dangers serial killers pose to society. Some of the findings are that serial killer does not always live a life of a loner, and some understudy of serial killers found out some of them live a family life. Several serial killers were abused as children and from dysfunctional families and social backgrounds. Most serial killers are men and there is a patriarchal domineering and controlling personality, ascribed to serial killers.

Keywords: serial killer, social, psycho, organised and disorganised, murder, modus operandi, violence, South Africa.

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1. Introduction

Much of the general public's knowledge concerning serial murder is a product of Hollywood productions. Storylines are created to heighten the interest of audiences, rather than to accurately portray serial murder. By focusing on the atrocities, inflicted on victims by "deranged" offenders, the public is captivated by the criminals and their crimes. This only lends more confusion to the true dynamics of serial murder [1].

A serial killer is conventionally defined as a person who murders three or more people in a period of over a month, with a "cooling down" time between murders. For a serial killer, the murders must be separate events, which are most often driven by a psychological thrill or pleasure. Serial killers often lack empathy and guilt, and most often become egocentric individuals; these characteristics classify certain serial killers as psychopaths. Serial killers often employ a "mask of sanity" to hide their true psychopathic tendencies and appear normal, even charming [2].

One of the widely held motives of serial killers is that several of them according to previous research were subjected to severe neglect and abused as children [3]. Serial killers were often physically or sexually abused as children or witnessed the abuse of family members. The author highlights this hypothesis by arguing that not all neglected and abused children turn out to be serial killers. Another widely discussed hypothesis is that serial killers are insane and mentally deranged people and so do not have a mind of their own to determine what is wrong and right in terms of criminal responsibility. A view that is consistent with biological explanations that specific brain dysfunctionality may be responsible for serial murders. A fundamental dysfunctional in psychopathy is linked to the section of the brain, called the Amygdala, an area of the brain that is primarily responsible for emotional processing and functioning [4] An analysis of different disorders, including narcissistic personality disorder, antisocial personality disorder, borderline personality disorder, and dissociative identity disorder, promote a deeper understanding of motivations and methods, exhibited by serial killers. It is

important to discuss mental disorders that are relevant states of mind when talking about the thought processes and behaviors of violent offenders like serial killers [5]. Many serial killers have active fantasy lives, starting in early childhood. Many serial killers can be classified as narcissistic due to their self-absorbed nature and distance from other people in their lives [6].

The biological integrity and the brain function level are the bases for upcoming cognitive and emotional filters that will form a person's bio-psycho-social balance and construct his/her personality. It is a dynamic structure and never a passive, static characteristic. This is the foundation of the behavior sciences, including forensic psychiatry and psychology. In this matter, there are 2 plans of assessment of personality, especially in the case of serial killers and those are the personality components and personality types, each being formed in biological, psychological, and social directions [7]. Although, some serial killers were diagnosed as psychopaths by both psychologists and psychiatrists as suffering from mental disorders or psychotic and neurotic related illnesses. There are other factors at play when it comes to a full medical assessment of a serial killer. For example, factors of social background, environmental contexts, failure to conform to social norms, levels of irritability, anger, aggressiveness, and showing a lack of remorse [8]. The author argues that Psychopaths are not always insane people – they do know right from wrong. If the crime scene shows evidence of careful planning, the killer is likely to be intelligent and older. If the victim was mutilated in a very disorganized way, his/her killer is probably schizophrenic, and schizophrenics are more likely to be very thin and unkempt. Serial killers can be grouped into two headings as follows: organised and disorganised offenders.

The organized offender is described as leading an orderly life that is also reflected in the way he/she commits his/her crimes. Highlighting some proposed characteristics, he/she is claimed to be of average to high intelligence, socially competent, and more likely than the disorganized offender to have skilled employment. It is also claimed, that he/she is apt to plan his/her offenses, use restraints on his/her victim, and bring a weapon with him/her to commit the murder and take the weapon away with him/her from the crime scene [9]. Many serial killers, even those who are incredibly organized and methodical, slip up in some way that leads to their arrest by the police.

The disorganised offender is described as reflecting an overall sense of disorder and suggests little, if any, preplanning of the murder. The disarray present at the crime scene may include evidence, such as blood, semen, fingerprints, and the murder weapon. There is minimal use of restraints, and the body is often displayed in open view. The disorganized offender is thought to be socially incompetent and to have below-average intelligence [10]. While Douglas et al. (1992) hypothesize that the disorganized offender kills opportunistically. He or she will live in proximity to the crime scene. A lack of planning before, during, or after the crime will be reflected in the spontaneous style of the offense and the chaotic state of the crime scene. This mirrors the offender's social inadequacy and inability to maintain interpersonal relationships. The lack of normal, healthy social relationships increases the likelihood of sexual ignorance as well as the potential for sexual perversions or dysfunctions as part of the homicidal act [11]

Aim of research

The research has two aims. First was to highlight the nature of the risks of harm Serial killers pose to members of the community. Second, an imperative need for the police to be more proactive when it comes to making our communities safer.

2. Materials and methods

This is qualitative research, relying on an extensive review of the literature and exploring in detail case studies of South Africa's worst serial killers. A case study involves an in-depth investigation of a contemporary, real-life phenomenon in its context. A case study can focus on one person, a group, an organisation or event. Case study research is good for understanding complex issues in real-life settings, and it is often used to understand the perspective of participants in those settings. The characteristics of a case study are:

- a. A case that is bounded or defined in time, space, and activity.
- b. A context-based study of the phenomenon, rather than a study, conducted in a lab or through modelling.

- c. Multiple sources of evidence.
- d. A research problem/question that cannot be answered, relying on numerical data alone.

3. Results and discussions

A serial killer keeps killing until one of four things happens: /she is caught, he/she dies, he/she kills him/herself or he/she burns out. Serial killers have their own unique modus operandi. The MO reflects what the killer had to do to commit the crime. This includes everything from luring and restraining their victim to the way that they murder them. A serial killer's MO can change over time. Essentially, he/she learns from past mistakes and improves with time on how to carry out the crime with some accuracy and perfection. The MO is a criminal behavioral pattern, style, or technique that works for the criminal. This can be explained by using a hypothetical scenario of a football player who uses his skillful footballing techniques to score goals and make them recognised in their profession. Such footballers will continue to use their own techniques that work for them, improve them, and become excellent in it because it enhances their performance on the field. Serial killers are more likely to use and continue to use the modus operandi that works for them to evade arrest from law enforcement officers. The MO becomes their unique trademark of criminal ingenuity until they are apprehended by the police. The investigators must therefore establish the MO of a serial killer at the earliest possible time, it sets out the scene of who may be responsible for the crime. If the detection of MO of the serial killer is not detected on time, many more deaths are likely to happen. Serial killers hardly stop killings of their own volition. Most of them kill, kill, and kill several victims until they get caught or in some instances turn themselves up to the police after being exhausted from their killing spree journey. According to FBI profiler John Douglas, a signature "is a ritual, something the subject does intentionally for emotional satisfaction - something that isn't necessary to perpetuate the crime" [12]. Most researchers agree that there is no easy way to cure a serial killer. Some serial killers who spent time in mental institutions after committing their crimes or received psychiatric treatment were deemed "cured" and released, but they went on to kill again. Others did not improve after several treatment attempts.

Types of serial killers

Several types of serial killers have been proposed and analysed by previous researchers. The author will highlight only five typologies of serial killers in this study as follows:

1. The visionary type – responding to delusional voices to kill certain types of people.
2. Mission-oriented type – in which the murderer targets certain groups of evil individuals, such as prostitutes or a particular ethnic group.
3. Hedonistic type – in which the murderer seeks pleasure or thrills in the killing.
4. The control type – who wants to have power over the victims.
5. The predator type – who resembles the hunter of animals and engages in killing as a recreational activity [13].

Serial Killers in South Africa Contexts

South Africa has a fair share of several worst serial killers. Time and space do not allow the author to revisit each one of them. One can simply argue that serial killers in South Africa are not so much as publicised in South Africa when compared to the United States where serial killers out of their notoriety have several movies to their names. The author argues that serial killers should not be given a cult of celebrity status by the media because their crimes are despicable and heinous. But for the benefit of this article. The author will discuss some of the following serial killers in South Africa as follows: Moses Sithole; Cedrick Maake; Bulelani Mabhayi; Siphon Thwala; Jack Mogale; Christopher Zikode; Stewart Wiken; Petros Madiba, Gert Van Royen and Loius van schoor.

Moses Sithole (the ABC murderer -38 murders between 1994–1995)

Moses Sithole was born in Voslorus, a poor neighbourhood of Boksburg, Gauteng South Africa. His father died when he was five soon after, his mother abandoned him and the family. Sithole and his siblings spent the next three years in an orphanage home, where they were mistreated. He ran back to his mother, who sent him back to the orphanage. He began raping women in his twenties, arrested after the third rape. He was sent to prison for rape, whilst in prison, Sithole was sexually assaulted by other inmates. In 1994, he was released from prison to begin his murder spree

amounted to 38 total murders. Sithole carried out killings in Atteridgeville Pretoria, Boksburg, and Cleveland. Sithole MO was baiting women by offering them jobs at a children's home in Benoni. He went as far as to invent a fictional charity organisation. Once he had gained their trust, he would offer to walk them through an open field to the business headquarters. He would overpower, rape, and strangle them with their own underwear. In August 1995, Sithole was identified as a potential suspect on the run from the police, he called journalist Tamsen de Beer and identified himself as the wanted killer. A meeting was arranged but he did not show up because sensed a trap and ran, the police shot him twice when he charged them with an axe, wounding him before taking him into custody. He confessed to all 38 murders, making him the worst serial killer in the history of South Africa. On December 5, 1997, Sithole was sentenced to 2,410 years for the murders of 38 people, committed within the year 1994–1995. He committed 40 rapes, which add up to 12 years for each of the 40 rapes, 50 years for each of the 38 murders, and another 5 years for each of the 6 robberies. Sentences do not run concurrently and no possibility of parole. In 2000, he was reported to have HIV aids in Pretoria Prison. Whilst in Prison, another trait of Sithole's self-hate was reported, his serious dislike for black women was the major motive in his murder spree as most of his victims were black women [14].

Sithole's case study analysis

The author noted the following: first, Sithole's social family background was a disorganised and dysfunctional one with the absence of a caregiver from an early age. Sithole's abandonment by his mother was very crucial to his anger, frustration, and hate for women. He saw women as enemies, not to be trusted due to his history of maternal deprivation. There is an element of vengeance and lust for power and control over women. One can safely argue that Sithole grew up a psychologically damaged child, in which social services also failed to intervene, he stays at the orphanage home and tells a story of a failed social services system. Sithole was intelligent, charming, and persuasive, his ability to form a fictional employment agency to lure and bait women, winning their trust, shows some amount of intelligence, strategy, and organisational skills. His ability to commit 38 unstoppable murders within a year shows his resilience to being evil. The call he made to the journalist Tamsen de Beer shows Sithole's overconfidence and arrogance, a kind of come and get me if you can, mentality and cockiness. He took law enforcement effectiveness for granted as his murder spree counts of 38 deaths, exhibited by his bravado and invincibility. At the time of his arrest, we are informed that he charged the arresting officers with an axe, this shows that Sithole was a very violent man and would do anything out of desperation to enjoy his freedom. It also shows how and what ordeal and the level of violence all his 38 victims must have been subjected to by strangulation. His confession of hating black women whilst in prison is an expression of self-hate and a victim of aids, which he may have contracted during his raping spree. The author has no mercy for Sithole and fully supports the verdict of no possibility of parole. Sithole remains the worst serial in South African history then and now. The author warns all women to be more vigilant and not be deceived by promises of jobs from strangers as there are still many more Sithole's out there who would like to take advantage of defenceless women, looking for jobs in South Africa. As there is nothing stopping any other potential criminal from repeating the modus operandi of Moses Sithole [15].

Cedrick Maake A.K.A the Wemmer Pan Killer (27 murders)

Cedrick Maake, born in 1965, was one of South Africa's most elusive serial killers, as he constantly changed his modus operandi. A married father of four children and a part-time painter. In some cases, he shot couples to death in their own cars, and in others, he bludgeoned his victims to death with rocks. Maake was described as a "unique serial killer". Unlike most multiple murderers, he did not fixate on one type of victim or method and his motives remain a mystery. His victims ranged from a 74-year-old tailor he murdered with a hammer to a 15-year-old teenager on her way home from a disco with her boyfriend. The murders were so varied, with no underlining pattern of gender, age, or race, that the police at the time believed they were investigating at least two different serial killers. Maake's gruesome murders emerged in court. The surviving female victim narrated her ordeal in the hands of Maake as follows: he would sometimes kick and scream obscenities at his victims, while they were lying on the ground in a near-death situation and used

large rocks to crush the head of his victims. During the trial, he would sometimes display verbal outbursts, weeping whenever his mother was mentioned, suicidally slamming his head against the dock. On one occasion, he threatened a female state prosecutor that she will go through the same experiences as his female victims.

In 1998, Maake was finally caught when he sold a bicycle at a pawn shop. The bike had been stolen from one Gerhard Lavoo, murdered in 1997. When the police found the pawn shop receipt they realised that Maake, who had been arrested a few weeks earlier for attempted murder and rape, was the man behind the grim murder spree. He was finally arrested in the December of 1997 in Gauteng and was convicted of 27 murders, 26 attempted murders, 14 rapes, and 41 aggravated robberies. He maintained his innocence during the trial, claiming that there was a conspiracy against him. Maake is currently serving out a 1 340-year-long prison term [16].

Maake's case study analysis

The author explains that little information is known about Maake's upbringing and early life. This presents a barrier when it comes to profiling him and finding out the motives for his crime. Maake kills for fun and falls into the category of a sadistic serial killer. A sadistic serial killer as the author understands it, derives pleasure in harming others and that pleasure is often sexual. They often torture their victims and deliberately keep them in excruciating pain before ending their lives. Unfavorable childhood experiences in early childhood are a possible cause of sadistic personality. One can become a sadistic killer through learning and observation within their social and environmental contexts. Maake displays signs of a mentally deranged suicidal serial killer, not in touch with reality, delusional at times, to the extent of threatening a female state prosecutor during the trial. The author concurs with the judge's long-term prison verdict, handed over to Maake for his atrocities and inhumane murders.

Bulelani Mabhayi also known as Monster of Tholeni Butterworth Eastern Cape (20 murders 2007–2011)

Bulelani Mabhayi, born in 1974, is a South African serial killer. His victims were mainly women and children. Mabhayi would break into houses at night where there were no men, he would rape his vulnerable victims 11 women and 9 children, and then kill them with a panga or an axe. His youngest victim was 14 months old and his eldest was 79 years old [17]. In 2011, shoe prints, accidentally smeared in one of his victim's bloods, led to Mabhayi's arrest. He has an abnormal large shoe print, which was not common in the village. In 2012, Mabhayi was sentenced to 25 life sentences after pleading guilty to 36 charges, 20 of murder, six of rape, and 10 of housebreaking. Tholeni is an isolated village between two major cities in the Eastern Cape province. This made tracking Mabhayi down a difficult task. Forced to extreme measures, the police took fingerprints and DNA samples from hundreds of males in Tholeni. However, Mabhayi did not have an identity document and his fingerprints couldn't be matched to anything. By that time, the "Monster" had already murdered 15 victims. He simply carried on and killed five more people before he made a mistake. Leaving his shoe print behind next to his last victim meant the end of his reign of terror.

Mabhay's case study analysis

Mabhay is a shameless opportunistic serial killer. He is a coward who selects his victims from the household where there were no men to resist him. The killing of children also shows he had no good childhood experience, possibly a pedophile with a sexual abuse history. Mabhay is a sexual predator, hunting for women and children to devour at any given opportunity. It highlights the plight of women in our society, subjected by men to endure high levels of femicide. The killing of women in South Africa has currently reached an unacceptable crescendo. There is a societal failure to protect women in South Africa [18].

Sipho Thwala also known as the "Phoenix Strangler" (19 murders) 1996–1997

Sipho Thwala, born in 1968, became the most wanted man in Kwa Zulu Natal during a year-long killing spree in the sugarcane fields of Mount Edgecombe, near the small Phoenix Durban. The Killer's Modus operandi was to lure his victims into sugar farms, promising jobs as domestic servants in nearby hotels, rape and kill them using their underwear to tie them, then strangle and bludgeon them to death before burying them in shallow graves. His murders began gaining attention because he was very public about erasing evidence – he would set alight the sugarcane field he

had just murdered his victim in to destroy all traces of the crime. He was acquitted of rape and murder charges in 1994-the same year the first victim was found in a cane field. Thwala was arrested in 1997 after the South African Police matched his DNA sample with the one, found on one of his victims [19], [20]. On March 31, 1999, the High Court Durban found Thwala guilty of 19 murders, and 16 rapes between 1996-1997. He was sentenced to 506 years in prison.

Thwala's case study analysis

Sipho Thwala was an opportunist serial killer who lured women, promising employment. The vulnerability of women in South Africa is again highlighted where women must fend for themselves and provide for their families. The safety of women is compromised due to economic disparity and the hardships women must endure. Men in some instances are not able to cater to their families due to the high unemployment rate. In some households, women have become both the caregiver and the providers for the family. Thwala and his likes serial killers preyed on women's vulnerability and economic deprivation to perpetuate unlawful killings on them. Thwala's MO of destroying the sugar cane field (scene of a crime) to conceal or destroy his links with the crime scene is a characteristic of an organised offender [21]

Jack Mogale (West end serial Killer with 16 murders from -2008–2009)

Between 2008 and 2009, the residents of West Johannesburg experienced a spate of killings. No one could guess that the person responsible for it was a man, working as a preacher, or at least a pretender to all his victims to be a preacher. Mogale lured a total of 15 women and one child to deserted fields of Westonaria, Venterspost, and Lenasia. He would normally wear a Zion Christian Church badge or Sangoma beads, claiming to be a prophet, sent by God to heal would-be clients. He struck his victims with blunt objects, tied them with their underwear, beat them with bricks, then raped and strangled them. Many of his victims were found partially naked near the West End Clay Bricks Factory in Zuurbekom where Mogale lived. He was arrested in March 2009. Mogale was nailed by DNA evidence admissions of two women who survived his killing spree. It was his fiancée, the main state witness Charlotte Manaka who gave a testimony, contradicting all Mogale's evidence that helped the state to secure his convictions. Mogale denied all the charges against him and claimed that he was framed by the police. One of his alleged victims was 19 years old when Mogale battered her face with a brick, while raping her in an open field in Westonaria. She testified that she had accepted a lift from Mogale and only realised that she was in danger when he took the wrong turn and became aggressive when she asked where they were going? After the rape, Mogale left her unconscious and bleeding in the field. She only woke up the following day and crawled to a nearby road where she was able to get help. Bodies of his victims were mostly left in sexual positions, naked and raped. At the time of arrest, he showed his manhood to a policewoman and said "when I come out from here you will be the first person I rape and kill" During his trial, Mogale sat smiling, grinning, and even laughed out loud. Mogale was found guilty of 9 kidnappings, 19 rapes, 16 murders, 3 robberies with aggravating circumstances, sexual assault, and an escape from lawful custody. Sentenced to 16 life imprisonment sentences, with no possibility of parole.

Mogale's case study analysis

Mogale is a vile and horrible person, as physical injuries, sustained by some of his victims, portray a vivid picture of a very sick man, psychopath, and sexual predator who prey on women. Mogale deserves no mercy. It was reported, that Mogale exposed his private part to the female police officer and threatens to rape and kill her too, which shows the indebtedness of his mental instability. Mogale was no prophet of God but an imposter and a devil's prophet.

Christopher Zikode is also known as "Donnybrook Serial Killer" (18 murders) 1994-1995

Donnybrook is a tiny village in Kwa Zulu Natal, South Africa, rich with its tribal cultures and traditions where one such tradition includes faction fights. Christopher Mhlengwa Zikode was born in the year 1974 in this village under a tribal family. He grew up, witnessing his family fight ferociously with the enemy tribe. He even learned how to use modernized guns during the fight. His father taught him all sorts of defense artworks along with a detailed course on how to kill a human clean. Never did he know that his son would turn into an expert serial killer. Zikode grew up to be one of the finest fighters in their tribal group. However, his aim was not to diminish the rival tribes. His mother had died, while giving birth to him, hence he was taken care of by the men

in his family. Thus, the only women he met in his life were the tribal girls. His modus operandi was to choose the women from church reception, locate their house and kick the door in, to everyone's shock. As a precautionary and first step, he would shoot all the men and boys of the house until they were dead. Later he would drag the women onto the plantation fields nearby and rape them for up to five hours constantly. If any of them try to resist him he would shoot and kill them at first and later perform necrophilia. He committed eight murders, five rapes, five attempted murders, and one indecent assault. Zikode was charged with over twenty-one crimes and his case was cracked open by South Africa's finest forensic profiler and psychologist, Dr. Micki Pistorius. His file was studied, and he helped in the proceedings that followed Zikode's arrest. According to Pistorius, Zikode possessed a sexual urgency that was carved out of ruthless torture and inhumanity. He enjoyed torturing women, while performing intercourse with them. Zikode was sentenced to five life sentences, totalling 140 years in prison [22].

Zikode's case study analysis

The author wishes to state that Zikode's father should be held partly responsible for socialising him into cultural violence. There is nothing wrong with one celebrating their cultural heritage, but children must not be socialised into violence under the guise of cultural traditions. This is a clear case of social learning, gone wrong.

Stewart Wilken (Bootie Boer) 10 murders 1990–1997

Stewart Wilken, born in 1966, preyed on the street children and women of Port Elizabeth Eastern cape from 1990 to 1997. His first wife Lynne narrated how she was in a very abusive relationship with Wilken whom she had a son, called Wuane. After the birth of their son, Wilken would only have anal sex with her in unusual and discomforting positions. Wilken confessed to murdering 10 people, including his 11-year-old daughter, and five counts of sodomy. But the state prosecutor failed to prove beyond a reasonable doubt that the two skeletons and a decomposed body, found where Wilken said he had sodomised and killed three street children, were those of his victims. Wilken also admitted to eating the flesh of one of his victims in a crazed drug state after becoming addicted to dagga and mandrax. He cut off the nipples of his fourth victim, a 42-year-old woman, and swallowed them. Wilken during testimony in court gave a graphic detailed account of how in the act of strangling his victims, he experienced sexual climax - even if the victim was dead. On one occasion returned to the dead body of his victim to have sex with it. Wilken was sentenced to seven terms of life imprisonment [23].

Wilkens's case study analysis

A serial killer with sodomy desires is not only aggressive but fantasises about this kind of sexual pleasure insatiable desires. They can no longer get satisfaction from human beings but turn on animals for their sexual pleasure. In some instances, they can only be sexually aroused when they cause pain and suffering to their victims. Some of them have been subjected to sexual abuse as a child. The eating of nipples is an act of cannibalism. It shows Wilkens's state of the mind. What drives a person to eat another human being is the extraordinary circumstances, associated with human beings. This becomes a demonic or ritualistic process of appeasing the king of the darkness. Having sex with the dead, an act of necrophilia, is very common amongst serial killers, especially those who kill for trophies or for recreational motives. The authors draw the conclusion that Wilkens is a very sick psychopath, detached from human reality. Wilkens should not have been allowed to raise a child, an early social services intervention to protect the child needed to be put in place. The absence of such intervention cost the life of the child. The duty to protect children is a recognised universal state legal duty. The author calls for a complete overhaul of the social services department in South Africa, taking into cognisance early warning systems, especially when dealing with vulnerable children, placed at high risk.

Petros Madiba

Petrus Madiba not only murdered eight women and a baby, but he also put the blame for his horrific crimes on them. For each murder, he had a different story. First, he claimed that six of the women were in a relationship with him at some point. He admitted to killing all eight women but said it was because they either stole from him or cheated on him. His reason for murdering the little baby girl, named Phologo Mokwena (and her mother), was that he allegedly found out the child was

not his as the mother claimed. However, the family of the woman confirmed this to be a lie, saying she met him the same day he killed her. Tragically, Madiba committed these murders while on bail for yet another murder. In October 2013, he was sentenced to a lifetime in prison.

Madiba's case study analysis

The author argues that when an offender puts blame on his victims, it shows that such offender is not accepting their criminal responsibility, showing a lack of remorse, and unwillingness to deal with their offending behaviour. Madiba committed some of these murders whilst on bail. This shows a failure of the criminal justice system and the ineffective bail system that was put in place to monitor the activities of Madiba. The murdering of a child shows that Madiba is psychotic, vengeful, and very violent [24]

Gert Van Royen

Just about everyone in South Africa knows about the serial killer and paedophile Gert van Rooyen. Mothers still relate the horrific story to their daughters when teaching them to stay away from strangers. Van Rooyen's violent crime spree began in 1979 when he kidnapped two young girls. He forced them to take their clothes off and perform various sexual acts on him. He let them go the next day. Gert van Rooyen was almost immediately arrested, tried, and convicted, then sent to prison for four years. He was released after three. Time in jail did little to rehabilitate van Rooyen. He started dating Joey Haarhof in 1988, and she helped him lure his next victims to their home. Between 1988 and 1990 Joey even contacted several children's homes and told staff she wanted to "look after" young girls for holiday periods and weekends. In 1990, Haarhof decided to abduct Joan Booysen, who was 16 at the time. Luckily, Joan managed to escape, even after being drugged and sexually assaulted. After Booysen alerted the police, they placed the house of van Rooyen and Haarhof under surveillance. When Gert van Rooyen became aware of this, he saw no way out other than shooting his lover and then himself. To this day, none of his victims have ever been found.

Gert Van Royen's case study analysis

This is a good case study, supporting the view that prison does not work when it comes to the rehabilitation of serious offenders. The delay of the police in apprehending Van Royen may have led to more avoidable deaths. Was placing van Royen under surveillance the best the police could have done to save lives under the circumstances, given above? From 1979–1990 is such a long time to allow Van Royen to roam about his community, knowing that he posed sexual and violent danger to citizens. The license to roam about freely provided Van Royen a platform to take more lives. The author is of the opinion that proactive policing was absent in this case as the police knew who van Royen was.

Louis van Schoor

Louis van Schoor took the term "trigger happy" to a whole new level. Starting his career out as a police officer and ending up as a security guard, van Schoor was convicted of seven murders in 1992. Before his conviction, it was thought that he killed as many as 39 people. He even admitted to shooting 100 people after setting traps for them in the form of silent alarms. He was known as an apartheid killer since he only murdered black victims. Alarming, van Schoor's daughter apparently inherited her father's murderous genes. Sabrina van Schoor hired a hitman to murder her own mother in 2002. She was caught, convicted, and handed a life sentence. Contrary to her father, Sabrina believed her mother was a racist and deserved to die. Louis van Schoor and his daughter ended up in the same prison. Curiously, Louis only served 12 years of his 20-year prison sentence. He was released on parole in 2004, leaving his daughter behind to serve the rest of her life term. Van Schoor walked out of prison smiling, ready to marry his fifth wife and "go farming."

Van Schoor case study analysis

The author opined that the criminal justice system treated Van Schoor leniently. He served 12 years out of his 20-year prison sentence. What happened to the remainder 8 years? This may be also because Van Schoor was an ex-policeman. The myth of biological or inherited criminality (born criminal) is highlighted in this case study.

There are a variety of serial killers, from sexual predators to psychotic killers, from murder teams to odd eccentric stalkers, to present the distinct psychological dynamics that set serial killers apart from other violent murderers. Among the motives addressed are lust, control, glory, profit,

thrill, delusions, rage, the desire for company, the need to please a partner, and even murder as an intellectual exercise. Some serial killers live double lives, hiding their violence even from those who live with them. One theory that has been stressed in relation to serial killer's motives is the diathesis-stress model. It states that all serial killers have a propensity to act and think in a certain way due to environmental stressors. Through a combination of other factors such as self-esteem and self-control coupled with social skill issues, the person retreats into a more withdrawn state. The killer, at that point, believes that they can correct their problems through killing. Crime is a mental activity; criminals make choices as adults with the mental capacity to make choices. We cannot detect sex killers by their appearances, domestic circumstances, or day-to-day behaviour. The sexual impulse is also primarily a mental process, like murder, it begins inside the head. It is a closely guarded secret; we only get the opportunity to investigate the minds of the sex killer when they are arrested. Sexual killers fantasize prior to their actual killings. They strive to perfect their modus operandi, approaching each killing with some element of sophistication, refining their techniques and cover-ups of their tracks as they go along. The author is optimistic that proactive policing, supported by intelligence-led policing, profiling, and psychologically effective police investigative training alongside information technology support, can disrupt the activities of serial killers.

4. Conclusion

In discussing some of the results of the study above. The author is faced with several important but unanswered questions for future researchers to investigate further the secretive world of serial killers. Some of these questions for future research are: to what extent can our social services department in South Africa hold claim to rendering excellent service delivery to vulnerable children placed in care homes? For example, Moses Sithole, one of the serial killers, discussed above, we found out that him and his brother were both placed in care and where abused whilst under care. The author calls for a more rigorous police check and clearance for people who work with vulnerable persons or group in our society. Members of staff who abuse children under their care should be punished severely. One of the author's limitations is that the study would have been deemed more reliable and valid if the author was given the opportunity to speak to serial killers via a supervised prison visit. Although these poses serious risks to both the researcher and the prison authorities as most serial killers are placed in maximum security category prison because they are classified as very high-risk offenders. The author recommends that the future researcher should consider carrying a semi structured interviews with serial killers, but they must not compromise their life and safety when doing so.

Conflict of interest

The author has no conflict of interest in relation to this article.

Acknowledgments

The author dedicates this article to all victims of serial killers in South Africa. They died because law enforcement could not prevent some of the avoidable deaths. Predators will always prey on their victims, seeking for any slightest opportunity to pounce on their hunted preys. Law enforcement officers must be one step ahead of them. Police officers should become hunters of minds more than human hunters. Stop serial killers before they go on a killing spree. The use of technology to fight crime must effectively be deployed to stop serial killers before they even strike, relying on vis a vis intelligence led policing.

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